

RAINFALL-DRIVEN NUTRIENT DYNAMICS IN AGRICULTURE**Shrushti Hosmani, Vaishali D N, Vijeta Vishwanath Hegde,**Students, Department of Computer Science & Engineering, Bangalore Institute of Technology,
Bengaluru-560004**Prof. Chaithra G V,**Assistant Professor, Department of Computer Science & Engineering, Bangalore Institute of Technology,
Bengaluru-560004**ABSTRACT**

Efficient fertilizer management is essential for enhancing agricultural yields and minimizing nutrient loss, yet farmers often lack precise guidance for optimal usage. This research explores the relationship between rainfall patterns and nutrient loss, highlighting how rainfall impacts fertilizer efficiency. While moderate rainfall aids in dissolving and delivering nutrients like nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium to the plant roots, excessive rainfall leads to runoff and nutrient leaching. By machine learning, this study proposes a solution to optimize fertilizer use based on crop-specific requirements and rainfall data. Using Random Forest algorithm combined with K-fold cross-validation, the model predicts the ideal nutrient composition and timing for fertilizer application. Farmers input their crop type and location into the system, and the model forecasts the precise nutrient quantities required while identifying the optimal fertilization period. The model is implemented on a web platform built with Flask, enabling easy access and usability across devices. This method helps enhance soil fertility, minimize nutrient depletion, and support sustainable farming practices.

INTRODUCTION

Agriculture plays a pivotal role in driving national economic growth, ranking second globally in farm outputs. Fertilizers are most needed for replenishing nutrients extracted by crops from the soil's top layer, ensuring sustained agricultural productivity. A lack of proper fertilization can significantly reduce crop yields. However, effective fertilization requires precision, considering factors like rainfall trends and soil nutrient requirements for crops. Leveraging machine learning offers a modern solution to these challenges by analyzing data related to fertility of a crop and rainfall pattern. Farmers can benefit from accurate, data-driven insights to enhance crop productivity.

This study introduces a machine learning model utilizing a Random Forest algorithm combined with k-fold cross-validation. The system requires two user inputs—crop type and location—and predicts the optimal nutrient quantities needed, the best timing for fertilizer application. The particular model is deployed via a Flask-based web application, ensuring cross-platform accessibility and user-friendly sharing. This approach aims to optimize fertilizer usage, improve crop health, and support sustainable agricultural practices.

RELATED WORKS

An in-depth study of the available literature presents a catalog of previous studies to deal with this issue. In [1], the authors demonstrate that prediction of fertilizer usage can indeed help the farmers achieve sustainable agriculture, reducing the risks of plant toxicity and nutrient deficiencies. Paper [2] makes application of fuzzy logic techniques that enable decreasing fertilizer use leading to affect crop yields. Additionally, [10] shows that the enhanced efficiency of fertilizers is not sufficient for complications that can be caused by compaction. These issues can be mitigated by enhancing the fertilizer recommendation, which requires the development of a measurable relationship under Nitrogen and Prosperous for fertilizer usage, in terms of agricultural yield, nitrogen requirement, and nitrate level which is given in [11] and paper [4] seconds this by providing a measure to estimate the weightage of nutrient requirements and also the role of the chemical properties of soil.

Forecasting crop yield is difficult because of unstable rainfall patterns and fluctuations in temperature. Some can apply different techniques as propounded in [3] for better crop yield prediction. In [5] state that nitrogen leaching is prone in areas that have no-till management and this may cause crop loss. In [7] the authors suggest a novel metric for 'soil health and quality' including refinement of soil's health.

IJETRM

International Journal of Engineering Technology Research & Management

Published By:

<https://www.ijetrm.com/>

The goal of the paper [8] Looks to assess the significant variations in the creation and elements of soil populaces and capabilities because of the collaboration between long haul treatment and precipitation variances, to decide if preparation history affects the water-obstruction of soil microorganisms. Also, Paper [13] predicts agricultural yield depends on rainfall. This is accomplished by giving a general summary of how production is affected by rainfall and how much a given crop can yield given the Rainfall accumulation. The suggested evaluation approach is Stronger than existing methods, as it takes into account all regression techniques

In paper [6] predict the yield of practically all kinds of crops in India. This script creatively utilizes simple parameters like state, district, and area to enable users to estimate harvest outcomes for any particular year. Paper [12] makes use of Transfer Learning techniques (TLT) to develop a pre-trained model for identifying patterns within the dataset, which was thereafter employed for crop yield prediction. In [14], supervised algorithms are applied to enhance crop yields, minimize human effort, save time and energy on various farming activities, and provide plant recommendations tailored to specific soil properties, offering a comprehensive approach to predicting crop sustainability. The research in [16] highlights the capabilities of machine learning models to analyze and interpret results, providing great insights for long-term fertilizer studies, with these methods being applicable to other extended experiments. Paper [17] introduces a decision-making system that leverages crop, and pesticide/insecticide data.

In [18], present an in-depth approach to addressing pre-cultivation activities in agriculture. The study aims to help small-scale farms operate more efficiently, achieve higher yields, and reduce production costs. It also provides a way to estimate overall growth expenses, enabling better forward planning. Integrating pre-cultivation processes offers a holistic solution to agricultural challenges. In [19], address Difficulties in nutrient profiling of soil by applying the Extreme Learning Machine (ELM), a fast-learning classification method that utilizes different activation functions

Crop diseases significantly affect overall yield. Paper explores this issue through an IoT-based study which is happened in the Kashmir Valley. It introduces a model for predicting apple diseases using machine learning and data analysis techniques. Additionally, the study explores the difficulties of incorporating advanced technologies into conventional farming methods.

EXISTING SYSTEM

- Existing systems that address the challenges of optimizing fertilizer use amid varying rainfall patterns include several advanced tools and strategies.
- Precision agriculture tools, such as GPS and sensors, allow for targeted fertilizer application based on specific soil needs, reducing waste.
- Weather forecasting models provide real-time rainfall predictions, helping farmers time their fertilizer applications more effectively.
- Soil moisture sensors and variable rate technology (VRT) further enhance this process by detecting optimal conditions and adjusting application rates across different field zones.
- Integrated Nutrient Management (INM) combines organic and inorganic fertilizers to improve nutrient retention and soil health, while decision support systems (DSS) provide tailored guidance on retention and soil health, while decision support systems (DSS) provide tailored guidance on fertilizer use based on various factors like crop type and weather forecasts.
- Additionally, rainfall-triggered fertilizer systems can automatically adjust applications based on real-time rainfall data. Crop simulation models estimate how crops will respond to fertilizer under different rainfall scenarios, aiding in better planning.
- Despite advancements, existing systems have drawbacks. Precision agriculture tools and VRT can be costly and require experience that may be inaccessible to small-scale farmers.
- Weather forecasting models and soil moisture sensors are not always accurate, leading to suboptimal fertilizer application.
- Controlled-release fertilizers can be expensive, and their effectiveness depends on soil types. Decision-making aids and extension programs often struggle to reach farmers in remote or underprivileged areas, reducing their overall effectiveness.

IJETRM

International Journal of Engineering Technology Research & Management

Published By:

<https://www.ijetrm.com/>

PROPOSED MODEL

This research presents a predictive model aimed at estimating the nutrient needs of crops using the Random Forest algorithm. This model integrates Random Forest with the k-fold cross-validation technique to ensure accurate predictions. During the evaluation process, acceptable accuracy levels are established, validating the model's effectiveness. 7 different features are considered to know the algorithm's performance.

As you can see in Fig. 3.1, the system takes user inputs, including crop type and location. The location data is processed through a Weather API, which provides environmental conditions like temperature (temp), humidity (H), and rainfall (R). If heavy rainfall is predicted, a warning is shown to the farmers. else, the proposed algorithm proceeds to calculate the required nutrients, ensuring precise and tailored recommendations.

Random Forest Algorithm

Random Forest algorithm is A machine learning method that constructs several decision trees, with each tree trained on different subsets of data and varying hyperparameters. In our project, we apply this method to predict the values of Nitrogen, Phosphorous, and potassium based on the crop type and location specified by the former. The dataset is initially split into two parts: 80% for training and 20% for testing. Separate Random Forest models, each consisting of 50 decision trees, are constructed for predicting Nitrogen, Phosphorous, and potassium values. The final prediction for each nutrient is Gained by averaging the outputs of all the trees in the respective models.

Input Features

- Crops: such as rice, orange, lentil, cotton and others.
- Temperature: recorded in degrees Celsius.
- Humidity: expressed as a percentage.
- Rainfall: measured in millimeters.

Output Features

- Label N: The concentration of nitrogen Found in soil.
- Label P: The concentration of Phosphorous Found in soil
- Label K: The concentration of Potassium Found in soil

Data Preparation

The original dataset includes eight features, but not all feature of them are relevant to the model building. To look into this, a feature selection technique is employed, reducing the dimensionality and identifying seven significant features for further analysis

IJETRM

International Journal of Engineering Technology Research & Management

Published By:

<https://www.ijetrm.com/>

Fig 1.0: Project Flow

BEGIN:
Step 1: The dataset, consisting of 2200 records, partitioned into training and testing sets. The training dataset makes up 80% of total (1760 records), while the test dataset comprises the remaining 20% (440 records).
Step 2: Random forest regression is applied separately to the N (Nitrogen), P (Phosphorus), and K (Potassium) features. For this, 50 estimators (decision trees) are used, with each tree contributing to the model's predictions.
Step 3: The training data is employed to create separate models for each dependent variable (N, P, and K). Here, the dependent variable corresponds to N for the N, P for the P, and K for the K.
Step 4: For each target label (N, P, K), the random forest regression generates predictions based on an ensemble of 50 decision trees trained on the respective training data.
END

Algorithm

IJETRM

International Journal of Engineering Technology Research & Management

Published By:

<https://www.ijetrm.com/>

Fig 2.0: Block Diagram

CONCLUSION

This research aims to provide an intelligent and optimistic decision for the farm system to optimize fertilizer usage. In conclusion, this research presents a robust and scalable model for optimizing nutrient application in agriculture, using rainfall data to guide fertilizer recommendations. By employing the random forest algorithm and incorporating user input for crop type and location, the model adapts nutrient suggestions to diverse conditions, making it accessible for farmers and agricultural specialists across different regions. Beyond boosting productivity, this approach promotes environmental sustainability by minimizing the risk of nutrient leaching and runoff, thus preserving soil health. The model aligns with precision agriculture goals, delivering targeted recommendations that increase yields without excessive fertilizer use, which could otherwise harm soil quality over time. Additionally, this model offers economic advantages by helping farmers reduce unnecessary fertilizer costs while achieving optimal crop growth. Future iterations could further enhance the model's accuracy by incorporating additional climatic variables and crop-specific growth stages, making it even more responsive to real-time conditions. As climate change continues to affect rainfall and weather patterns, this model represents a very helpful tool for helping farmers adapt to fluctuating environmental conditions, contributing to resilient and sustainable agricultural practices.

REFERENCES

- [1] Krutika Hampannavar, Vijay Bhajantri, Shashikumar G. Totad "Prediction of Crop Fertilizer Consumption," Fourth International Conference on Computing Communication Control and Automation (ICCUBEA), 2018, PP.1-5
- [2] G. Prabakaran, D. Vaithyanathan, and Madhavi Ganesa, "A fuzzy decision support system for enhancing crop productivity and optimizing fertilizer use," *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, vol. 150, 2018, pp. 88-97.
- [3] Shital Bhojani and Nirav Bhatt, "Data mining approaches for predicting crop yields," *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, vol. 6, 2018, pp. 357- 358.
- [4] Yulong Yin, Hao Ying, Huifang Zhen, Qingsong Zhang, Yanfang Xue, and Zhenling Li, "Estimating NPK fertilizer requirements for rice cultivation across various environments in China under optimal fertilization rates," *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology*, vol. 279, 2019, pp. 1-6.
- [5] Laura J.T. Hess, Eve-Lyn S. Hinckley, G. Philip Robertson, and Pamela A. Matson, "Increased rainfall intensity leads to higher nitrate leaching in tilled systems, but not in no-till cropping systems in the U.S. Midwest," *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, vol. 290, 2020, pp. 1-10.
- [6] Potnuru Sai Nishant, Pinapa Sai Venkat, Bollu Lakshmi Avinash, and B. Jabber, "Machine learning-based crop yield prediction

IJETRM

International Journal of Engineering Technology Research & Management

Published By:

<https://www.ijetrm.com/>

for Indian agriculture,” *2020 International Conference on Emerging Technology (INCET)*, 2020, pp. 1-4.

[7] Tony Yang, Kadambot H.M. Siddique, and Kui Liu, “Impact of cropping systems on soil health in agriculture,” *Global Ecology and Conservation*, vol. 23, year, pp. 1-13.

[8] János Kátai, Ágnes Oláh Zsuposné, Magdolna Tállai, and Tarek Alshaal, “Can fertilization history increase the resistance of soil microbial communities and their activities to rainfall variations?” *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety*, vol. 201, 2020, pp. 1-11.

[9] Usman Ahmed, Jerry Chun-Wei Lin, Gautam Srivastava, and Youcef Djenouri, “A nutrient recommendation system for soil fertilization utilizing evolutionary computation,” *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, vol. 189, 2021, pp. 1-7.

[10] A. Hussein, Diogenes L. Antille, Shreevatsa Kodur, Guangnan Chen, and Jeff N. Tullberg, “Effects of controlled traffic farming on grain sorghum productivity, rainfall, and fertilizer nitrogen efficiency,” *Journal of Agriculture and Food Research*, vol. 3, 2021, pp. 1-17.

[11] Zujiao Shi, Donghua Liu, Miao Liu, Muhammad Bilal Hafeez, Pengfei Wen, Xiaoli Wang, Rui Wang, Xudong Zhang, and Jun Li, “Optimizing fertilizer recommendations to control nitrate residues in a wheat maize double cropping system under dryland farming,” *Field Crops Research*, vol. 271, 2021, pp. 1-10.

[12] Janmejy Pant, R.P. Pant, Manoj Kumar Singh, Devesh Pratap Singh, and Himanshu Pant, “Utilizing statistical machine learning techniques for agricultural crop yield prediction,” *Materials Today: Proceedings*, vol. 46, 2021, pp. 1-10.

[13] Benny Antony, “Crop production prediction based on rainfall patterns,” *Environmental Research*, vol. 202, 2021, pp. 1-5.

[14] Akash Manish Lad, K. Mani Bharathi, B. Akash Saravanan, and R. Karthik, “Key factors influencing agriculture and crop yield estimation through supervised learning algorithms,” *Materials Today: Proceedings*, 2022, pp. 1- 10.

[15] Raves Akhtar and Shabbir Ahmad Sofi, “Precision agriculture through IoT data analytics and machine learning,” *Journal of King Saud University - Computer and Information Sciences*, 2021, pp. 1-17

[16] Saheed Garnaik, Prasanna Kumar Samant, Mitali Mandal, Tushar Ranjan Mohanty, Sanat Kumar Dwibedi, Ranjan Kumar Patra, Kiran Kumar Mohapatra, R.H. Wanjari, Debadatta Sethi, Dipaka Ranjan Sena, Tek Bahadur Sapkota, Jagmohan Nayak, Sridhar Patra, Chiter Mal Parihar, Hari Sankar Nayak, “Exploring the impact of soil quality on rice yield through a 16-year long-term fertilizer study using conditional random forest,” *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, vol. 197, 2022, pp. 1-10.

[17] Rubby Aworka, Lontsi Saadio Cedric, Wilfried Yves Hamilton Adoni, Jérémie Thouakessah Zoueu, Franck Kalala Mutombo, Charles Lebon Mberi Kimpolo, Tarik Nahhal, Moez Krichen, “An agricultural decision support system utilizing advanced machine learning models for yield prediction: A case study from East African countries,” *Smart Agricultural Technology*, vol. 3, 2022, pp. 1-9.

[18] Senthil Kumar Swami Durai, Mary Divya Shamili, “Implementing smart farming with Machine Learning and Deep Learning techniques,” *Decision Analytics Journal*, vol. 2, 2022, pp. 1-30.

[19] M.S. Suchithra, Maya L. Pai, “Enhancing prediction accuracy in soil nutrient classification through optimization of extreme learning machine parameters,” *Information Processing in Agriculture*, vol. 7, 2022, pp. 1-11.

[20] Kaggle, “Crop recommendation dataset,” available at: <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/atharvaingle/crop-recommendation-dataset>.